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Public Service Innovation in the Best Practice Perspective at the Investment and One-Stop Services Office of Riau Province

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Abstract

This paper is a research study on the science of public administration that analyzes public service innovation from the perspective of best practices at the Riau Province Investment and One-Stop Services Service and analyzes the factors that hinder the implementation of public services based on best practices innovation at the Investment and Investment Service. One-Stop Service for Riau Province. The problems that occurred became the driving force for the authors to conduct research that aims to analyze the process of implementing public service innovations from the perspective of Best Practices at the Investment Service and One-Stop Integrated Services of Riau Province in 2020-2021 and look at the factors that hinder the implementation of public service innovations at the aforementioned agencies. The type of research used in this research is qualitative with data sources derived from two types of data sources, namely primary data in the form of interviews with informants and secondary data obtained through the process of observing and searching for documents that occurred during the research process. The results of the research will be found in how the mechanism of public services at the Capital Services and One-Stop Integrated Services and various obstacles that cause problems with the provision of public services so that they are by public services in the perspective of Best Practice. namely primary data in the form of interviews with informants and secondary data obtained through the process of observing and searching for documents that occurred during the research process. The results of the research will be found in how the mechanism of public services at the Capital Services and One-Stop Integrated Services and various obstacles that cause problems with the provision of public services so that they are by public services in the perspective of Best Practice. namely primary data in the form of interviews with informants and secondary data obtained through the process of observing and searching for documents that occurred during the research process. The results of the research will be found in how the mechanism of public services at the Capital Services and One-Stop Integrated Services and various obstacles that cause problems with the provision of public services so that they are by public services in the perspective of Best Practice.

Keywords: Innovation, Public Service, Best Practice, Riau Province

1. Introduction

Riau Province has 12 administrative areas, Cities, and Regencies which have regional autonomy functions. The rapid development that is taking place in Riau Province is of course supported by various parties such as the investment climate in Riau Province which is growing. The development of the level of domestic and foreign investment in Riau Province has also become one of the problems that the Riau Provincial government has so far faced, namely regarding licensing and non-licensing issues. Licensing is a document and proof of legality that permits legal action by a person or group of people within the realm of state administrative law for an act that is prohibited under statutory regulations. While the Integrated Licensing Service is the implementation of licensing services whose management starts from the application stage to the document issuance stage carried out by the Riau Province Integrated Licensing Service Agency. For licensing and non-licensing problems in Riau Province, the Riau Provincial Government made several breakthroughs aimed at facilitating the process of managing the licensing and non-licensing bureaucracy for the community and investors. It is hoped that the ease of licensing and non-licensing arrangements will further encourage the development of investment activities in Riau Province.

The policy trajectory of privileging innovation as a means to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of public services in the UK has moved at a rapid pace. This commitment has increased as the extent of the economic recession and its impact on public spending has been revealed (Patterson et al., 2009, p. 12). However, the same research also identified that the current economic climate may lead to a focus on less risky types of innovation, regardless of the level of comparative need. *Until now, the problem of public services has become a common concern, a formula is needed in the form of innovation so that public services become even better. Public service innovation has now become a demand that must be carried out by service providers, be it at the central or local government level. Every government agency is required to improve public services to the community in the form of existing innovations. The culture of innovation must be attached to the government that organizes services must be dynamic and always evolving because nowadays with a high level of literacy the public has understood and understood their rights and obligations in public services. High quality services are the main concern of public organizations. Information disclosure, when associated with service activities, has helped to make people more aware of their rights and obligations. Therefore, the expectation to be able to get the best service is now also starting to depend on government organizations.*

Service Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Riau Province as a government institution that provides licensing services to the public must of course lead to efficient, effective, and open work completion as a form of public accountability in realizing a climate of good governance. Public services based on Law No. 25 of 2009 is an activity or series of activities in the context of fulfilling service needs by statutory regulations for every citizen and resident for goods, services, or administrative services provided by public service providers. This understanding indicates that public service is a series of activities carried out by the government to fulfill the basic needs of every citizen.

The current implementation of public services is by the developing public service paradigm, namely the New Public Service (NPS). The New Public Service (NPS) paradigm views the public as citizens or citizens who have the same rights and public obligations. Not only as a customer who is seen by his ability to buy or pay for products or services. Citizens are recipients and users of public services provided by the government and are also subject to various public obligations such as complying with laws and regulations, paying taxes, defending the country, and so on. Diversity in public services encourages the creation of innovative services. Innovative service can be associated with public service innovation. According to Damanpour in Yogi Suwarno, innovation can be in the form of new products or services, new technology, new production process technology, new structural and administrative systems, or new plans for organizational members.

Public service innovation has developed a lot in Indonesia along with regional autonomy. As stated by Supriyono in Abdullah, broad autonomy has given enormous authority to local governments (districts/cities) to regulate and manage the provision of public services by the local choice and local voice of the people (Afrizal, Munaf, Y., Yogia, M.A., Suri, D.M., Prayuda, R., Amri, P. (2023). This mechanism has been widely used by

government agencies. The use of public service innovation has provided best practice public service innovation, such as in Gorontalo with the application of entrepreneurial values in the bureaucracy, and the Jembrana district of Bali, which is famous for its budget efficiency policies through innovative programs in the education and health sectors. *Best Practices* application of public service innovations, in addition to the Jembrana and Gorontalo areas, has also been developed in other areas. Development of public service innovation best practices, among others, such as the implementation of Electronic Government in Sragen Regency. The success of implementing Electronic Government in Sragen Regency is supported by several factors including Leadership with a clear vision, Involvement of all parties, preparation of human resources, gradual implementation, partnership building, and regular evaluation.

Public services based on Law No. 25 of 2009 are activities or a series of activities in order to fulfill service needs in accordance with laws and regulations for every citizen and resident for goods, services, or administrative services provided by public service providers. This definition indicates that public service is a series of activities carried out by the government in order to fulfill the basic needs of every citizen. The implementation of public services is currently in accordance with the developing public service paradigm, namely the New Public Service (NPS). The New Public Service (NPS) paradigm views the public as citizens or citizens who have the same public rights and obligations. Not only as a customer who is seen from his ability to buy or pay for products or services. Citizens are recipients and users of public services provided by the government and at the same time are also subjects of various public obligations such as complying with laws and regulations, paying taxes, defending the State, and so on.

Diversity in public services encourages the creation of innovative services. Innovative services can be associated with public service innovation. According to Damanpour in Yogi Suwarno, innovation can be in the form of new products or services, new technology, new production process technology, new structural and administrative systems or new plans for organizational members. Authority is the right granted by the Riau Provincial Government to do or not to do something to the Head of the Integrated Licensing Services Agency to achieve certain goals. Delegation of authority to sign licensing and non-licensing from the Riau Provincial government to the Head of the Riau Province Integrated Licensing Service Agency based on Governor Regulation Number 26 of 2010 in its implementation there are still several administrative obstacles. Until now, there have been several authorities to sign licensing and non-licensing delegated to the Head of the Riau Province Integrated Licensing Services Agency from the Riau Province Regional Apparatus Work Unit, which can be seen in the following table:

Table. 1.1 Types of Delegation of Licensing and Non-Licensing Authority from the Provincial Government of Riau to the Investment Service and One-Stop Integrated Services

NO	Type of Delegation Authority to Sign Licensing and Non-Licensing to the Investment and One-Stop Services Office of Riau Province
1	Permit for Fisheries and Maritime Affairs
2	Livestock Sector Permit
3	Plantation Sector Permit
4	Mining and Energy Sector Permit
5	Industry and Trade Sector Permit
6	Permit for Agriculture and Food Crops and Horticulture
7	Permit for Land Transportation and Telecommunication Post
8	Public Works Sector Permit
9	Manpower, Transmigration, and Population Permits
10	Permit for Tourism and Culture
11	Forestry Sector Permit
12	Permit for Politics and Community Protection
13	Investment Sector Permit
14	Environmental Permit

Source: Governor Regulation Number 26 of 2010 concerning the Delegation of authority to sign licensing and non-licensing from the Riau Provincial Government to the Head of the Riau Province Integrated Licensing Service Agency (BP2T).

The delegation of authority to sign licensing and non-licensing to the Head of the Riau Province Integrated Licensing Services Agency has been going on since 2010. However, the implementation of these regulations has not been implemented optimally. In carrying out the delegation of authority to sign permits, there are still several technical constraints, such as the lack of socialization of regulations to the public so that the public does not know about the bureaucratic mechanisms for licensing and non-licensing arrangements. Good and quality service has implications for community satisfaction which is a benchmark for the success of government administration. Every government agency is certainly closely related to aspects of public service, both services in the form of goods or services that are directly related to the community, always trying to provide satisfying services.

The issuance of the Regulation of the Minister of State for Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform (PAN-RB) No. 15 of 2008 concerning General Guidelines for Bureaucratic Reform shows the government's seriousness in taking the first steps towards implementing a clean government. All state institutions, from the central to the regional levels, must improve and improve the quality of services provided to the community to achieve the desires and aspirations of bureaucratic reform itself. The government is getting serious about reforming current governance with the issuance of Presidential Regulation (PP) Number 81 of 2010 concerning the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025 which forms the basis for Ministries/Institutions/Regional Governments to carry out bureaucratic reform to realize good governance. good governance.

Achievements in bureaucratic reform are the administration of government that is free from KKN, capacity building, and accountability as well as strengthening the orientation towards improving public services. This goal makes bureaucratic reform a step at the upstream level, namely a preventive step which in practice in developing countries and new industries is far more effective and has a long-lasting impact compared to curative corruption eradication (Arif cahyadi. 2016. Improving public services (public services) must receive the main attention of the government because public services are basic social rights from society's social rights or fundamental rights (DHAP Eldo, D Mutiarin. 2018). The government should not neglect the rights of the people to get the best service, because the duty and function of the state is to protect the people and fulfill all their needs to achieve social welfare. The government's rejection or deviation in the administration of public services is contrary to the 1945 Constitution.

Innovation in the public sector is more emphasized on the aspect of "improvement" resulting from these innovation activities, namely the government can provide public services more effectively, efficiently, and with quality, cheap, and affordable according to community needs. Innovation in the public sector is one way or even a "breakthrough" to overcome bottlenecks and organizational needs in the public sector. In addition to carrying out maximum services, both the central government and local governments are also required to innovate in the public sector in the areas described in Presidential Regulation (PP) Number 81 of 2010 concerning the Grand Design of Bureaucratic Reform 2010-2025. Currently, innovation in the delivery of public services is not only carried out at the central level but at the sub-district level, a service innovation is also needed to be able to meet the needs of the community in the field of public services.

Service performance concerns work results, work speed, work carried out by customer expectations, and timeliness in completing work. If this error is the reason for the occurrence of complaints that are often heard from the public related to government apparatus, apart from being convoluted due to a rigid bureaucracy, the behavior of the apparatus which is sometimes unfriendly, timeliness, quantity and quality of service are still very low.

Until now, public service issues have become a common concern, a formula is needed in the form of innovation so that public services can be even better. Public Service Innovation is now a demand that must be carried out by service providers, both at the Central Government and Regional Government levels. Every government agency is required to improve public services to the community in the form of existing innovations. The culture of innovation must be attached to the government that provides services that must be dynamic and always evolving because at present, with a high level of literature, the public understands and understands their rights and obligations in public services. Implementing DPMPSTSP Riau Province has the intent and purpose of providing

easy licensing and non-licensing services to the community by the principles of good governance. There are many types of services available including the investment service and one-stop integrated services, namely as many as 18 types of services, both licensing and non-licensing.

Every customer (community) has the same right to good public service. Poor service will result in them being dissatisfied, this can be caused by a lack/weak awareness of the tasks and work that is the responsibility of the leadership, staff, systems, procedures, and work methods that are inadequate so that the working mechanism does not work as expected, the organization of service tasks is not appropriate, the employee's income is not sufficient for their minimum living needs, the employee's ability is inadequate for the tasks assigned to him, and adequate service facilities are not available. Several public views on services at the Investment and One-Stop Services Office of Riau Province show the impression that customer (community) complaints occur due to slow officer service, convoluted procedures, non-transparency, collusion, discrimination, uncertainty, long waits, and protracted -late, while what they want is convenience in managing their interests, getting reasonable service, getting equal treatment without favoritism, getting honest and forthright treatment.

Low service performance will create a bad image for government agencies, where dissatisfied customers (the public) will tell others (negative word of mouth). Conversely, the higher the service performance, the added value will spread positively (positive word of mouth) which is difficult for organizations to control because they are satisfied with their services. Seeing this requires innovation in the public sector, especially DPMPSTP, to put more emphasis on the "improvement" aspect resulting from these innovation activities, namely the government can provide public services more effectively, efficiently, and with quality, cheap, and affordable according to community needs. Innovation in the public sector is one way or even a "breakthrough" to overcome bottlenecks and organizational needs in the public sector. One of the Public Service Innovation Concepts that can be applied is the Best Practice concept.

2. Research Method

The type of research used in this research is qualitative, which describes the actual situation of what was there at the time of the research based on the author's observations in the field by collecting data, clarifying, and analyzing it so that an analysis formulation of the problems encountered is obtained. Then with the qualitative research method, this method seeks to provide an overview of the situation in the field so that this method aims to accumulate data and draw conclusions from the research (Rauf, R., Prayuda, R., Munaf, Y. (2023). According to Sugiyono, the qualitative research method is often called the naturalistic research method because the research is carried out in natural conditions (natural setting), also known as the ethnographic method because initially this method was more widely used for research in the field of cultural anthropology, referred to as a qualitative method because the data collected is more qualitative analysis (Sugiyono, D. (2010).

A research location is a place where researchers conduct research, especially in capturing phenomena or events that occur from the object under study to obtain accurate research data. As for the author's research location, namely: Investment Service and One-Stop Integrated Services of Riau Province. The research data sources include: Primary data, namely data obtained directly from informants (respondents). In this research, data were obtained directly from the research location using face-to-face meetings. Secondary data is data obtained from various sources in Investment and One-Stop Service Office of Riau Province in the form of regulatory documents related to public services, this is adjusted to research needs

3. Results and Discussion

Good and quality service has implications for community satisfaction which is a benchmark for the success of government administration. Every government agency is certainly closely related to aspects of public service, both services in the form of goods or services that are directly related to the community, always trying to provide satisfying services (Pertiwi, R. (2012). Commitments related to Bureaucratic Reform are not only at the level of the central government but even at the lowest levels of government, they must begin to organize their

governance systems that can prioritize the interests and satisfaction of the people with services, including the District Government of Sekalipun. Even though the sub-district government is not the last line of defense in the delivery of public services, the role of the sub-district government is very important as an extension of the district government (Prasojo, Eko, Teguh kurniawan dan Azwar Hasan (2007).

Some public views on services at the Riau Province One-Stop Investment and Integrated Services Office show the impression that customer (community) complaints occur because officer services are slow, convoluted procedures, non-transparent, collusion, discrimination, uncertainty, long waits, and protracted, while what they want is convenience in managing interests, getting reasonable service, getting the same treatment without favoritism, getting honest and straightforward treatment. The Riau Province One-Stop Investment and Integrated Service Office as a government institution that provides licensing services to the public must certainly lead to the completion of efficient, effective and open work as a form of public accountability in realizing a good governance climate.

A best practice can be defined as an efficient and effective method of accomplishing a task, based on repeatable rules that have proven effective for many people over a long period of time. The term best practice is often used to describe the process of developing a standard method of doing something that can be used by various organizations such as in the fields of management, policy, or software systems. A good public service process is directly related to the results of good policy implementation. However, policies are considered good if they are able to be understood thoroughly or clearly by all parties in the tripartite concept. The clarity of the policy itself can be characterized by its transparency in planning until the end of evaluation. The implementation and development of best practice public service innovations, among others, the successful implementation of Electronic Government is supported by several factors including:

1. Strong political leadership with a clear vision.

Change management, to overcome organizational and cultural problems can only be done well with the support of strong leadership. Organizational and cultural challenges are generally more difficult to resolve than technological challenges. Change management is necessary to ensure the success of e-government implementation.

2. Involvement of all parties.

Strong leadership has provided a good climate to raise mutual awareness of the importance of all parties' support for e-government. The early stages of implementation were not without obstacles. The initial opening of the Integrated Service Office (KPT) has led to cynicism from many parties. The adoption of innovation, in this case KPT, if it has not been proven to be useful is often met with resistance. However, when the innovation has been proven, it will be easy to get the support of many parties. Involving all parties will reduce this resistance.

3. Human resource preparation.

In e-government implementation, one of the most obvious obstacles in the early stages is the capability of human resources. In addition, another major problem is changing the mindset. Training, consultation, and comparative studies to several private companies were conducted. Even the uniforms of staff at the KPT are not far from the uniforms of employees in private companies such as banks. To deal with the problem of individual capability, information technology training is conducted regularly. Each Head of Department must even be accompanied by a trained operator.

4. Phased implementation.

Phased implementation is another lesson learned. KPT is a good choice to start e-government implementation. Apart from involving many parties, the impact on public services can be felt immediately. Besides being able to deal with limited resources, this gradual implementation will also facilitate the diffusion process by reducing risks and lowering resistance.

5. Partnership building.

Partnerships with various parties were developed. For example, the application for ID card printing is the result of a profit-sharing collaboration with a private company. Thus, the investment that must be spent is not too large without sacrificing service quality.

6. Conduct regular evaluations.

To measure the success of e-government, the Sragen Regency Government conducts regular evaluations although they are still limited to the quality of public services provided by KPT. Every year, KPT conducts a survey to service users, to measure quality, and at the same time get feedback for improvement. Based on the supporting factors for the successful implementation of Electronic Governance above, several supporting factors for success are used as benchmarks for determining the factors that are the strengths and weaknesses of implementing innovation, namely: leadership with a strong vision, involvement of all parties, preparation of human resources, regular evaluation. Best Practice in public services, in fact, cannot be concluded in one institution or one research study alone. The assessment of whether or not the implementation of public policy is good or not is not only focused on how the government and the bureaucratic institutions under it carry out the service process, but is broadly related to participation and change in society. So it cannot be concluded that a service process is good or bad only by looking at its implementation, but also by assessing active participation by the community.

The DPMPTSP Office has conducted online licensing regarding the issuance of permit recommendation letters, but the facts in the field are that there are still complaints and complaints from the public both directly and through the mass media, such as: complicated procedures, complaints about the length of permit issuance and data verification related to permit recommendations, and this is exacerbated by the absence of confirmation from the agency regarding the length of issuance so that students become confused and wonder about the cause of the length of time the permit is issued, whether there is an error in entering data or other causes.

Through the use of the online system there is also a problem that there are several sites listed in the requirements that must be downloaded through the DPMPTSP website that are difficult to access, the telephone address that cannot be contacted makes a bad image for licensing services. Seeing this, innovation is needed in the public sector, especially DPMPTSP, so that it emphasizes the "improvement" aspect resulting from these innovation activities, namely the government is able to provide public services more effectively, efficiently and with quality, cheap and affordable according to community needs. Innovation in the public sector is one way or even a "breakthrough" to overcome congestion and organizational needs in the public sector. One of the Public Service Innovation Concepts that can be applied is the concept of Best Practice.

Based on the data obtained from the results of the interviews conducted, the implementation of public service innovation in the Best Practice Perspective at the Investment Service and One-Stop Integrated Services of Riau Province in 2020-2021. There is a flow or service procedure that must be passed to get service at the Investment and One-Stop Services Office (DPMPTSP) of Riau Province. The requirements needed for services are available on the table and have also been framed and attached to the wall in the room so that the public can see or also take photos of the administrative requirements that you want to make. The procedure to go through to get service at DPMPTSP is starting with visiting the reception desk to convey the intention of obtaining the desired permit, then the applicant is required to fill out the guest book and take a queue number, the next step is to fill out the form that is addressed after that the applicant is instructed to wait until called to the administration desk. The community as an applicant can also ask for an explanation from the officer from the initial stage to the final stage of making permits.

On the aspect of facilities and infrastructure, the information provided by the informant was that the condition of the room in the Riau Province DPMPTSP service environment was very neat and clean. We provide the number one service. This can be seen we provide space and seats waiting for the community. Then the place for community consultation. We comply with service standards. As well as availability at our service point, of course, we provide a large waiting room. This is adjusted if there is a long queue. Then, there is also available wifi that can be used by the community for free (Holle, E. S. (2011). There is a special room for breastfeeding

mothers. Comfort is our priority. The conditions for Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the DPMPTSP environment in providing services are up to standard and up to date. The connection can now be connected to the central service. Also, people don't need to come to the office to take care of administration, they can go online. So we can provide services offline or at the office or online.

The service time at DPMPTSP for completion is by the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), namely the work is carried out on weekdays. And payment fees also follow the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), if there are additions, the applicant can make a report to the head of the Riau Province DPMPTSP. The speed and accuracy of completing documents received by the public adjusts the SOP and if it does not match the time according to the SOP, then it is the responsibility of the DPMPTSP of Riau Province. Information obtained regarding the spirit of cooperation and loyalty shows that employee discipline has been good. This can be seen in the fingerprint attendance used by DPMPTSP. Discipline employees in coming to the office and providing services can be on time. The attitude of employees and officers in providing services is good (Noor Khalifah. 2016). Over the past few years, there have been no complaints about the services we provide. However, if there are public complaints about our services, we can provide input to the office or the DPMPTSP Riau Province email. The concern of officers in the Riau Province DPMPTSP environment is good. Officers serve the community from the initial stages of service to the end of service. Then if there are further questions the officers provide a number that can be contacted so that people do not have to come to the office.

The ability and skills of officers in providing services can be seen when officers explain the programs requested by the community. If the community asks the officer immediately explains according to the community's request. To be fair providing this service depends on the community. If there is an injustice in providing services, you can contact the head of DPMPTSP Riau Province. Because all officers work according to the official SOP. Not all officers responded to requests from the community. Because officers work according to SOP. If it's not in the SOP, of course, the officer asks the superior first. The factors that become inhibiting the implementation through the use of the online system there is also the problem that there are several sites listed in the requirements that must be downloaded through the DPMPTSP website, which are difficult to access, telephone addresses that cannot be contacted create a bad image for licensing services. In addition to the problems above, there is also uncertainty regarding the completion of permits sent because based on statements in interviews stating that there is a possibility of delays in the completion of permits depending on the density of services or not, so this has caused dissatisfaction from the public who think that the DPMPTSP service is unable to accommodate a large number of permit applications. Lots. So it is very necessary to have improvements and innovations made to make it easier for the community to manage permits.

4. Conclusion

Commitments related to Bureaucratic Reform are not only at the level of the central government but even at the lowest levels of government, they must begin to organize their governance systems that can prioritize the interests and satisfaction of the people with services, including the District Government of Sekalipun. Even though the sub-district government is not the last line of defense in the delivery of public services, the role of the sub-district government is very important as an extension of the district government. Quality and high-quality services are the main concern of public organizations. Disclosure of information, when linked to service activities, helps encourage people to become more aware of their rights and obligations. Therefore, Facing licensing and non-licensing problems in Riau Province, the Riau Provincial Government made several breakthroughs aimed at facilitating the process of managing the licensing and non-licensing bureaucracy for the public and investors. It is hoped that the ease of licensing and non-licensing arrangements will further encourage the development of investment activities in Riau Province. However, the breakthroughs made will also bring up several obstacles that occur in this research, one form of the obstacle is the lack of public awareness of the importance of providing input and criticism of the DPMPTSP Service through the platform that has been provided.

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